

One additional set of XRF tests of reinked ink near 14 + 8 = 22 obeloi

One additional set of XRF tests could help determine whether there is original ink underlying the 14 not-yet XRF-tested obeloi on lines with a distigme and the corresponding 8 bars in Matthew that also extend into the margin at least 1.9 mm and are at least 3.8 mm long and have a gap in the text where other manuscripts insert at least four consecutive words.

Nehemia Gordon has already done this test for the obeloi at 1241 B9 and 1243 A12. Using Dino-lite images Gordon was able to identify places where reinking did not overlap original ink near these two obeloi. Gordon's XRF tests of these two obeloi demonstrate that part of those bars match the ink signature of original ink and that that ink is distinct from the ink used by the reinker. If similar XRF tests are done on re-inked ink near the other 14 obeloi on lines with a distigme and the corresponding 8 bars in Matthew, some of those tests might confirm not only that other obeloi contain original ink, but that the tested ink is distinct from nearby reinked text. This test would be important because Gordon has shown that the range of the copper-to-iron ratio of reinked ink throughout Vaticanus overlaps that same range as original ink. Tests of nearby reinked ink, however, can exclude the possibility that original ink obeloi could just be ink that was reinked.

In particular, Dino-lite images may not be able to identify any portion of some of these 14 + 8 = 22 obeloi that has not been reinked. In these instances, if there is a clear difference between the copper-to-iron ratio of nearby original and nearby reinked ink (e.g. 0.1 ratio in original ink vs. 0.2 ratio in reinked ink), even where it is not possible to test original ink in an obelos that has not been reinked, if the test result is significantly less than the copper to iron ratio of reinked ink, this will provide evidence that an underlying original-ink obelos best explains that lowered the overall copper-to-iron ratio.

This could be particularly helpful in the eight bars in Matthew that also extend into the margin at least 1.9 mm and are at least 3.8 mm long and have a gap in the text where other manuscripts insert at least four consecutive words. Statistically, it is likely that 2 or 3 of those 8 are merely paragraphoi that by coincidence occur where other manuscripts insert at least four consecutive words. This is because there are 211 instances in Matthew with bars that also extend into the margin at least 1.9 mm and are at least 3.8 mm long and have a gap in the text where other manuscripts insert at least four consecutive words. Since on average in Matthew one in 83.5 lines of text coincide with a NA28 or Swanson-listed variant where other manuscripts insert at least four consecutive words, out of 211 lines one should expect 2 or 3 at random will coincide with a four-or-more-consecutive word addition.

Consequently in every case where the original ink's copper-to-iron ratio is significantly different than that of the reinked ink, if even the lightest portion of any of those eight bars in Matthew has the same copper-to iron ratio as reinked ink and, then we could conclude that those bars are paragraphoi, not obeloi. But without testing nearby distinctly reinked ink, we could not make this distinction. For textual criticism, these additional XRF tests could provide further evidence of confirmed obeloi in the Vaticanus New Testament.

Summary of Needed XRF Tests listed in my article submitted to the *Vatican Library Review*

7.5 What XRF tests must be done to determine the originality of some distigmai and obeloi?

Seventy-four XRF tests on the following thirty-three Vaticanus pages (#1–33) are needed to determine the originality of some distigmai and obeloi. The remaining untested seventeen distigmai that look identical to the color and faintness of original Vaticanus ink and an unreinked letter on those pages must be tested to determine whether some or all of them match the ink signature of original Vaticanus ink on the same page:

#	Location L=left R=right M=margin D= dot	original ink location	letter	letter #
1	1336 A22 LM LD	1336 A39	Ω	2
2a	1339 C42 LM RD			
2b	1339 C42 RM RD	1339 C9 R vertical stroke of Ν	Ν	10
3	1349 B19 LM RD	1349 B23	€	7
4	1350 B18 RM LD	1350 A34	€	10
5	1355 B40 LM RD	1355 B24 R vertical stroke of Ν	Ν	8
6	1356 B24 LM RD	1356 B23	Ν	10
7	1357 C1 RM RD	1357 C1 R vertical stroke of Ν	Ν	8
8	1359 A32 RM LD	1359 A35	Ι	12
9	1368 C15 LM LD	1368 C22	Ο	8
19	1370 A32 LM LD	1370 A33	€	10
11	1383 A4 LM LD	1383 A14	€	7
12	1459 C41 RM LD	1459 C36	€	7
13a	1466 A25 LM RD	1466 A25	€	12
13b	1466 B6 LM RD			
14	1468 B3 LM LD	1468 B15	Η	13

32 1058 A31 vertical stroke of **B** or **P**

1058 A31 bar's left end

1058 A33 € 4

33 1066 C30 RM **o** or final **P**

1066 C30 left half of **O** 15

These 74 XRF tests (17 + 15) + (10 + 14 + 11) + (3 + 1 + 3) on 33 Vaticanus lines could establish definitively whether the ink of some distigmai match the ink signature of nearby original ink. They could also provide guidance for determining whether scribe B conjoined some distigmai with obeloi or penned only obeloi to mark multi-word insertions preserved in some manuscripts.

More detail regarding the needed XRF tests on Codex Vaticanus B distigmai and obeloi

I have clustered all of the XRF tests together that are on the same page of Vaticanus. If the Vatican already has XRF test results for unreinked original letters on any of those pages, those XRF tests will not be needed. Ideally the following four categories of 74 XRF tests will be done to find their ratio of Cu to Fe (Iron):

1. XRF testing of the 17 undisputed distigmai that actually match the color and faintness of original Vaticanus ink and for each, an unreinked letter near it in the sequence it was written. LM = left margin, RM = right margin, LD = left dot, RD = right dot. The smaller dot was selected unless there appeared to be a possibility that the smaller dot contains darker ink. Note that occasionally because of darker ink in the left vertical stem of a nu, the test should be done on its right vertical stem to avoid contamination from possible partial reinking. Total 33 XRF tests:

1336 A22 LM LD, **Ω** omega A39 2nd letter Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1336.

1339 C42 LM RD, **Ν** nu (right vertical stroke) C9 10th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1339.

1339 C42 RM RD, **Ν** nu (right vertical stroke) C9 10th letter (only one test needed, since this is the same as the test for 1339 C42 LM RD, **Ν**)

1349 B19 LM RD, **€** epsilon B23 7th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1349.

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1350 B18 RM LD, € epsilon A34 10th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1350.

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1355 B40 LM RD, Ν nu (right vertical stroke) B24 8th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1355.

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1356 B24 LM RD, Ν nu B23 10th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1356.

1357 C1 RM RD, Ν nu (right vertical stroke) C1 8th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1357.

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1359 A32 RM LD, Ι iota A35 4th letter from right.

1368 C15 LM LD, Ο omicron C22 8th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1368.

1370 A32 LM LD, € epsilon A33 10th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1370.

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1383 A4 LM LD, € epsilon A14 7th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1383.

1459 C41 RM LD, € epsilon C36 7th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1459.

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1466 A25 LM RD, € epsilon A25 12th letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1466.

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1466 B6 LM RD (Ν nu B11 9th letter, not essential if € epsilon A25 12th letter is tested)

1468 B3 LM LD, Η ēta B15 3rd letter from right. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1468.

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1475 B11 LM LD, € epsilon B10 2nd letter. Note that it is critical to test along the first half of thin horizontal bar prior to where the bar becomes darker and at least slightly separated from the left curving stroke of the epsilon. If there is not enough ink there, the lower middle portion of the bottom portion of the epsilon may be tested as long as it does not include any of the darker part of that curve where the ink stroke is broad.

Other unreinked letters are 1475 B13, *nu*, the 5th letter from the right end of B13, *nu*, the last letter in 1475 B27, and *epsilon*, the in 1475 B24.

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1499 C42 RM RD, € epsilon (half way down on its left curving stroke) C32 2nd letter. Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1499.

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2. 9 untested distigmai + 1 insufficiently tested distigme by lines with a characteristic bar that I have identified as an obelos need an XRF test taken across the middle of one of their two dots. I normally ask that the XRF test be performed on the smaller dot, since if that dot was reinked, that test would be more likely to test original ink. The purpose of these tests is to detect whether there is more than negligible Cu (> .01 Cu). If an earlier distigme with higher Cu content like the original Vaticanus ink (~.12 Cu) was reinked, Cu would be > .01. 10 pages. 22 or 23 XRF tests (23 if the thin strip of original ink above the left end of the bar at 1280 C10 can be XRF tested).

1241 B9 RD (see image below, FIGURE 14 from Gordon, Nehemia & Andrist, Patrick & Hahn, Oliver & Vasileiadis, Pavlos D. & Calvillo, Nelson & Rabin, Ira, Did the Original Scribes Write the *Distigmai* in Codex Vaticanus B of the Bible (*Vat. gr. 1209*)? in *The Vatican Library Review* 3 (2024), 125–156, © Vatican Library.

p. 146). Since the part of the original distigme that would have the least contamination from smeared ink is the light ink in the middle of the right dot, and because the space where the original dot would have been is elongated vertically, the ideal place to perform an XRF test with the highest probability of crossing through an original dot is vertically along the blue line through the middle of that right dot, where the ink is somewhat lighter. The right dot is above and slightly left of the horizontal bar that was reinked. [See the bar's original ink and its reinking below. Note that Gordon et al.'s 138 TABLE 1 XRF test was done *in between* the two smeared dots. It showed 0.02 Cu. Gordon 141 TABLE 3 identifies the unreinked original ink sigma at 1241 A24 to be 0.12 Cu. Gordon 146 TABLE 5 identifies the unreinked original ink sigma at 1241 A24 to be 0.12 Cu and 0.02 Zn and the original bar's ink to be 0.12 Cu 0.03 Zn.]

1241 B9 Vatlib image © Vatican Library

1253 B13 LD. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the left dot.

1253 B13. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the adjacent horizontal bar.

1259 A33 RD. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the right dot.

1259 A33. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the adjacent horizontal bar. [Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1259.](#)

1280 C10 RD. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the right dot.

1280 C10. Perform an XRF test on the faint strip of ink immediately above the far left end of the reinking of this horizontal bar where or slightly above where I added a blue line. This

strip of ink matches the color of nearby original Vaticanus ink in Gordon et al. 144
FIGURE 12 © Vatican Library, duplicated below:

It would be ideal if the path of the XRF test angled slightly upward so that it ends slightly above the right end of the blue line in the image above in order to avoid contamination from the darker reinking of the beginning of that horizontal bar.

If there is not enough ink to test this faint strip, test the apricot color ink below and to the left of the right end of the reinking of this bar or the faint middle portion of the horizontal bar.

1280 C9 3rd letter. Perform an XRF test in the left vertical stroke of the \aleph nu. [Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1280.](#)

1284 C12. Perform an XRF test vertically through the middle of the left dot.

1284 C12. Perform an XRF test near the middle of the horizontal bar at where the ink is faint.

[Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1284.](#)

1285 B12 on the faint ink immediately above the far right end of the reinked bar, which is on the right side of the vertical stroke of the ρ .

1305 A17 RD. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the right dot.

1305 A17. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the horizontal bar where its ink is faint.

1305 A7. Perform an XRF test on the € epsilon 1305 A7 12th letter. [Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1305.](#)

1361 C3 RM LD. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the left dot. Note that this dot is one line above the “8” with a dot on its right and a dot on its left.

1361 C3 LM. There appears to be some original ink on the top side of the far right end of the horizontal bar that crosses through the first letter (phi) of this line. Perform an XRF test on it only if there is enough faint ink for a successful XRF test.

© Vatican Library. If possible, perform an XRF test on the faint grey thin line of ink that protrudes at the far right of the top of the horizontal bar. The location of the XRF test should be just below the blue line I have added. I placed the blue line above where the XRF test should be performed so that the XRF tester will be able to see the thin strip of ink that appears to match the color of original Vaticanus ink. [Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1361.](#)

1371 C17 RM RD. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the right dot.

1371 C17 LM. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the horizontal bar under the left stem of the μ (mu), the 1st letter in this line. [Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1371.](#)

1385 B7 LM LD. Perform an XRF test vertically through the middle of the left dot.

1385 B7 LM. Perform an XRF test through the middle of the adjacent horizontal bar where its ink is faint.

1385 A36. Perform an XRF test in the right vertical stroke of the unreinked ν (nu), A36 last letter. [Gordon confirmed that no XRF test was done on 1385.](#)

1474 A20 LM RD. Perform an XRF test vertically through the middle of the right dot.

1474 A20 LM. Perform an XRF test on the faint portion of the horizontal bar under the first half of the κ (kappa), the first letter on 1474 A20.

1474 A22. Perform an XRF test on the unreinked € (epsilon), the 10th letter on 1474 A22.

3. The previous section requests XRF testing of nine of the thirteen obeloi with a gap in their line at the precise point some manuscripts insert at least four consecutive words regarding which Gordon et al. did not report any XRF test. The other four are [4 pages. 5 XRF tests]:

1243 C40. Perform an XRF test on the faint portion of the middle of the horizontal bar.
[Gordon 139 TABLE 2 XRF Cu 0.01 for both dots, Zn 0.01 right dot, Zn 0.00 left dot. Gordon 147 TABLE 6 1243 C20 unreinked *nu* Cu 0.10 Zn 0.01 Gordon 136 n. 70.]

1279 C41. Perform an XRF test on the middle of the horizontal bar, where the ink is faint.

1332 C20. Perform an XRF test near the middle of the horizontal bar at 1332 C20 where the ink is faint.

1390 A32 LM. Perform an XRF test on the middle of the horizontal bar. This is to see if it has negligible copper content like its distigme that Gordon already tested. If the ink signature of the horizontal bar matches that of the distigme, this will indicate that scribe's recognition that distigme-obelos symbols mark where some manuscripts preserve multi-word interruptions of the Vaticanus text.

- 1390 A38 8th letter. Perform an XRF test on this unreinked € epsilon. [Gordon's email identifies tests at 1390 A5, Omicron \(2 tests\); 1390 C40, Tau](#)

4. Tests in Isaiah of ink in obelos explanations:

1058 A31. Perform an XRF test on the vertical stroke of the unreinked beta (β) (or *rho* [ρ] if there is not enough ink in the unreinked *beta* [β] to test).

1058 A31. Perform an XRF test on the left end of the obelos.

1058 A31. Perform an XRF test on the left side of the unreinked original ink € *epsilon* at 1058 A31, the 4th letter on 1058 A31).
Our goal is to see if to see if their ink signatures match.

In 13 cases in the Vaticanus prophetic books, scribe B carefully penned tiny uncial text in the margin: **ΟΥΚ' Π' ΕΒ** where Vaticanus has no obelos: 988 A7*; 1033 B21, 37; 1034 B31*; 1035 C8; 1038 B15; 1045 C2, 38; 1046 A40*; 1054 C16*; 1066 C30*; 1073 C36*; 1074 B17*.

988 A7. Perform an XRF test on the vertical stroke of the *upsilon* (Υ) in the marginal **ΟΥΚ'**.

988 A7. Perform an XRF test on the middle angled stroke of *nu* (Ν, the 5th letter on 988 A7).

1066 C30. Perform an XRF test on the faint *omicron* (ο) in the right margin (or the final rho [ρ] in the right margin if there is not enough ink in the ο to test).

1066 C30. © Vatican Library. Perform an XRF test on the left angled stroke of the **Ο** omicron, the 15th letter on this line (1066 C30), the letter before the **Ν**, the first letter in the image above.

Note: The person doing the XRF testing may see magnified Vaticanus images at https://digi.vatlib.it/view/MSS_Vat.gr.1209 This is done by selecting that Vaticanus page number, dragging the white rectangle along the bottom of that page until that page number is visible, raising the magnification circle with 3 horizontal lines in it that is located on the right side of the top of that page to its highest level, and moving the red box in the small text image that is located on the right side of the bottom of that page to the part of that page the tester wishes to see magnified.